

and the latter, 273. At 35 days after transplanting the roots of treated seedlings had 4.7 nematodes/g root; the

roots in the check plots had 10.2 nematodes/g root. At harvest the former had 3 nematodes/plant and the

latter, 29/plant. Plots with the treated seedlings yielded 85% more than the check plots (1.5 kg vs 0.81 kg/plot). ■

Further studies on the potential of weeds to spread tungro in West Bengal, India

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In a previous study on the potential of weeds to spread rice tungro in West Bengal, no virus occurred naturally on the predominant graminaceous and cyperaceous weeds at the Kalyani virus experimental field. But *Echinochloa colona* and *Paspalum notatum* inoculated with the virus kept it for 3 months. In

a further study of weeds' potential for spreading rice tungro virus, weeds were collected from different locations early in different crop seasons.

The following weeds were collected in April 1978 and in June 1978: *Echinochloa colona*, *Paspalum notatum*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Eleusine indica*, *Cyperus iria*, *Imperata cylindrica*, *Setaria glauca*, *Sporobolus diander*, *Cyperus esculentus*, *Leersia hexandra*, *Dicanthium annulatum*, *Brachiaria ramosa*, and *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*. Only *L. hexandra* was not obtained in June but another species,

Digitaria sanguinalis, was available. In November 1978 only nine weeds (*E. colona*, *C. dactylon*, *P. notatum*, *S. diander*, *C. esculentus*, *D. annulatum*, *I. cylindrica*, *B. Ramosa*, and *Cyperus rotundus*) were collected. None showed any virus except a few collections of *E. colona* from the endemic fields of Malda.

The weeds were then inoculated with the tungro virus and their retention of the virus was indexed on TN1 seedlings (see table). The research was funded by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi. ■

Transmission of rice tungro virus from weeds collected 2 to 5 months after inoculation, Kalyani, West Bengal, India, 1978.

Weed	Transmission (%)											
	April				June				November			
	2 mo	3 mo	4 mo	5 mo	2 mo	3 mo	4 mo	5 mo	2 mo	3 mo	4 mo	5 mo
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	15	10	5	X	20	10	X	X	20	10	X	X
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	X	X	X	X	25	15	10	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	X	X	X	X	X	Y	X	X	20	10	X	X
<i>Cyperus iria</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	X	X	X	X	10	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i>	X	X	X	X	20	10	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Paspalum notatum</i>	X	X	X	X	30	20	10	X	10	X	X	X
<i>Setaria glauca</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Sporobolus diander</i>	X	X	X	X	10	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Cyperus esculentus</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Dicanthium annulatum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Brachiaria ramosa</i>	X	X	X	X	10	X	X	X	X	X	Y	X
<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

1979 setback for ufra

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Ufra disease, caused by the rice stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* (Filipjev) is serious in deepwater rice in southern Bangladesh. It was particularly severe around the village of Kashimpur in Comilla district, almost at the northern limit of its distribution in southeastern

Bangladesh, according to disease surveys in November 1977 and 1978. In 1979, the disease disappeared from the area; no plants with symptoms were found during September. The average number of nematodes per stem in 6 fields about

80 m apart along a linear transect at Kashimpur was estimated using the procedure described by Cox and Rahman (IRRN 4[3] June 1979:10) at about the end of September (i.e. just before panicle initiation) in 1979 and in 1979 (see

Average number of nematodes per stem in 6 deepwater rice fields along a transect at Kashimpur, Bangladesh, 1978 and 1979.

Date	Sample size (stems/field)	Nematodes (av no./stem)						
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2 Oct 1978	15	— ^a	1421 ^b	9	49	786 ^{bc}	250	989 ^b
24 Sep 1979	50	4	— ^a	1	1	6	1	1

^aNo deepwater rice. ^bIncludes stems containing more than 3,000 nematodes. ^cThis crop was a total loss because of ufra in 1978.

table). Although *D. angustus* was present in 1979, its number was small. The 1979 population was uniformly distributed along the transect despite large differences between fields in 1978. No heavily infested stems, which might provide evidence of primary infestation from diseased crop residues, were found in any of the fields in 1979. A similar sequence of events was observed at another northerly site between Dacca and Narsingdi.

The nematode overwinters in diseased crop residues and is reactivated by spring rainfall at about the time of sowing — late March and early April.

It appears that the water came too late for ufra in 1979, when there was a spring drought in Bangladesh. The total April rainfall at Joydebpur was 35.5 cm in 1977, 18.0 cm in 1978, but only 1.8 cm in 1979. Matlab Bazar in south Comilla, deep inside the ufra-affected area, had plants exhibiting symptoms of

ufra attack as early as July 1979. The deepwater rice there is sown a few weeks earlier than at Kashimpur as the fields soon become flooded by tidal movements from the river. These observations suggest that spring drought may hinder the northward migration of ufra and that control may be achieved, at least in part, by any procedure that prolongs the winter decay phase by even a few weeks. ■

Effect of length of time after leaf excision on tungro virus source

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When 1,280 adult *Nephotettix virescens* were provided access to tungro-diseased leaves at 0, 2, 4, 8, 24, 48, 72, and 92 hours after excision, the percentage of infective insects varied. The percentage of infective insects gradually decreased as time after excision increased; no insects became infective when access was 96 hours after excision (see figure). But insects were still able to acquire the virus from excised leaves after 72 hours, indicating that partly dried leaves can also serve as a virus source for the insect vector. ■

Effect of time after leaf excision of tungro diseased plant on percentage of infective *Nephotettix virescens*. IRRI.

Sheath rot spreads in Bihar, India

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Sheath rot of rice caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae* (revised as *Sarocladium oryzae*) was observed for the first time during 1977 kharif at ARI, Mithapur, Patna, in the National Screening Nursery (NSN) and International Rice Yield Nursery (IRYN) trials.

The disease had not been reported previously in Bihar. Oblong or somewhat irregular lesions were observed on the uppermost leaf sheaths enclosing the young panicles. Most of the lesions were dark brown, and some had light grey centers. The panicles of some infected tillers emerged only partially. Of 56 IRYN entries, 35 were infected. In 1978, 31.5 of 645 NSN entries at Mithapur farm were infected.

In the 1979 kharif, sheath blight was reported in all four RAU regional research institutes. ■

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Dirty panicles and rice yield reduction caused by bugs

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Species of the rice bugs *Riptortus*, *Stenocoris*, and *Aspavia* attack the rice grain from flowering to harvest and cause considerable crop losses in West Africa. The symptom of bug infestation is grain discoloration, generally described as *dirty panicle*. At Rokupr the feeding behavior of rice bugs and the nature of the damage they cause on rice were studied in 1- × 1- × 1.6-m field cages. *Aspavia* sp. and *Stenocoris* sp. at various densities were caged with the rice varieties CP4 and ROK5 from late booting to harvest. The cages were

checked daily and the different bug densities maintained until harvest. The grains were boiled for 5 minutes in 10% KOH solution; bug damage was then assessed.

Both nymphs and adults attacked the rice grains as soon as the panicle was exerted, and continued to feed on the developing grains until the hard dough stage. The bugs punctured the glumes and sucked the contents of the developing grain. *Riptortus* and *Stenocoris* fed on any site on the grain, but *Aspavia* tended to puncture the grain at the apical end. Only part of the grain milk was removed at each feeding and the same grain could be punctured several times. Fresh signs of *Riptortus* attack were stylet puncture marks, often with milk exudate, on the outer glumes. Those signs were not apparent in attacks